

Competitiveness thresholds for maritime methanol synthesis employing biogenic CO₂ emissions and renewable hydrogen

V. Mitrousis, E. Koliamitra, M. Bampaou^{*}, K.D. Panopoulos

Chemical Process and Energy Resources Institute (CPERI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH), 57001 Thessaloniki, Greece

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Bio-CO₂
Carbon capture and utilization
Methanol
Maritime fuel
Renewable hydrogen
Techno-economic

ABSTRACT

Decarbonizing maritime transport will require scalable renewable fuels and robust non-fossil carbon sources that can be supplied at industrial scales. In this context, dilute bio-CO₂ streams from biomass combustion plants represent a potential but underexplored renewable-carbon resource for e-methanol synthesis. This study evaluates the integrated production of maritime methanol from captured biogenic CO₂ and renewable hydrogen using process simulation and techno-economic assessment, employing a biomass CHP plant as real-world reference case to derive generalizable insights. Beyond a plant-specific evaluation, the analysis identifies system-level drivers of viability and competitiveness conditions across synthesis configuration, scale, electricity price, and electrolyser utilization. The results show total production costs of 1.10–1.43 €/kgMeOH, remaining above current fossil methanol bunker prices, with renewable hydrogen dominating the economics. Electricity procurement and electrolyser operation emerge as the principal levers: costs vary strongly with electricity price and improve with higher electrolyser capacity factors. Scale-up reduces unit costs but exhibits diminishing returns beyond the mid-scale range, indicating that infrastructure-enabled deployment could prove impactful than single-site scaling. Overall, the study suggests that biomass combustion plants may function as distributed renewable-carbon nodes for maritime e-fuel value chains, while highlighting that commercialization depends primarily on low-cost electricity, electrolyser utilization and coordinated carbon-hydrogen integration strategies.

1. Introduction

Maritime transport serves as the backbone of the global economy, conducting approximately 90% of international trade [1]. However, this scale of operation resulted in the sector contributing roughly 3% of global anthropogenic emissions in 2018, primarily due to the ongoing reliance on fossil fuels [2]. Their wide availability, low cost, and high energy density make them suitable for deep-sea vessels, and therefore the dominant option for that sector [3]. At the same time, recent political pressure has contributed to delays in finalizing the International Maritime Organization's (IMO) net-zero framework, creating uncertainty around the timing and stringency of future emission reduction regulations [4]. Nevertheless, with IMO forecasting a 90–130% increase in emissions by 2050 [5] and the recent implementation of the FuelEU maritime regulation setting progressively stricter targets for greenhouse gas (GHG) intensity reductions [6], the adoption of alternative renewable fuel options seems unavoidable.

Among the potential fuel options, green methanol has gained increasing interest as a carbon-neutral alternative [7]. Specifically, e-

methanol (e-MeOH) derived from biogenic CO₂ and green hydrogen can meet emission-reduction targets, since the constituting components are renewable and due to the favorable physicochemical properties, be adopted in existing maritime infrastructures with minimal changes [8–10]. In addition, methanol shares many properties with conventional marine fuels, with the most important being that it remains liquid at ambient temperature and pressure. This allows it to use existing distribution infrastructure with minor adjustments [9]. As a result, it can be stored in above-ground floating roof tanks and transported via sea, rail, and road tankers commonly used for liquid fuels. Methanol bunkering can be conducted through established approaches, including truck-to-ship, ship-to-ship, and terminal-to-ship, offering flexibility depending on demand scale and infrastructure availability [11,12]. However, in all cases, specific safety measures related to flammability [13], toxicity [10], and material compatibility [14] must be considered.

Existing literature indicates that e-MeOH currently remains above the fossil-derived MeOH market price levels, with reported production costs ranging from 0.56 [15] to over 4.5 €/kg [16]. This is largely due to differences in system boundaries, economic assumptions, reference years, production scales, and evaluation methods; most studies report

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: bampaou@certh.gr (M. Bampaou).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2026.108476>

Received 10 March 2026; Received in revised form 27 April 2026; Accepted 3 May 2026

Available online 8 May 2026

0378-3820/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Nomenclature

Acronym Explanation

AEL	Alkaline Electrolyser	MEA	Monoethanolamine
Bio-CO ₂	Biogenic Carbon Dioxide	NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
CAPEX	Capital Expenses	NOAK	Nth-of-a-kind
CEPCI	Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index	OPEX	Operational Expenses
CHP	Combined Heat and Power	PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
DeSOX	Desulphurization	PEM	Proton Exchange Membrane
DCC	Direct contact cooler	RES	Renewable Energy Source
DC	Direct costs	RFNBO	Renewable Fuel of Non-Biological Origin
FCI	Fixed Capital Investment	RWGS	Reverse Water Gas Shift
FOB	Free on Board	SN	Stoichiometric Number
GHG	Greenhouse Gas	TEA	Techno-Economic analysis
IC	Indirect Costs	TCI	Total Capital Investment
IMO	International Maritime Organization	TDC	Total Direct Costs
MeOH	Methanol	TIC	Total Indirect Costs
		TPC	Total Product Cost
		VLSFO	Very Low Sulphur Fuel Oil
		WCI	Working Capital Investment

values in the range of 0.8 and 1.6 €/kg [17–20]. For instance, Rahmat et al. [18] estimated a levelized cost of e-methanol between 1.13 and 1.48 €/kg for an e-MeOH plant in Germany, while Sollai et al. [19] and Meunier et al. [20] reported lower estimates of 0.96 €/kg and 0.81 €/kg, respectively. Conversely, a decentralized regional case study in the Netherlands by Gelten et al. [16] identified a significantly higher levelized cost between 4.06 and 4.51 €/kg due to more realistic regional market factors rather than optimistic theoretical assumptions. Despite these variations, the consensus across the literature indicates that the costs of producing green-H₂ are recognized as the primary bottleneck due to the capital intensity of electrolysis, coupled with high power demands. This challenge is further exacerbated when systems are directly integrated with intermittent renewable energy, which results in lower capacity factors and necessitates equipment oversizing [17].

Another factor to consider is that most existing TEAs focus on CO₂ derived from large-scale fossil point sources, such as cement [20–22], steel [23–25] and coal-fired power plants [15,17,19]. However, by 2040 the capture and utilization of CO₂ from fossil-based industrial point sources toward the production of renewable fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBOs) will not be acceptable for emission avoidance, effectively making bio-CO₂ the primary eligible carbon source for such pathways [26,27]. In spite of this regulatory push, there is a significant lack of research addressing the techno-economic challenges of utilizing biogenic sources. In addition, the limited number of TEA studies that consider bio-CO₂ based e-MeOH production focus on small-scale, high-purity sources, such as biogas upgrading and fermentation facilities [28–30]. In contrast, biomass-fired power plants represent a more viable pathway toward economies of scale due to their significantly higher total emission volumes and more decentralized nature [31]. However, they emit CO₂ in dilute flue gas streams (typically 3–12 vol%), rendering the application of energy-intensive capture technologies necessary [32,33]. In many cases, the captured streams also necessitate additional conditioning steps since they can contain impurities and trace components originating from the used biomass feedstocks [31,33].

The high costs of green hydrogen production, combined with the significant energy demands for capture and conditioning, increase the total production cost (TPC), making the commercial viability of e-methanol dependent on markets willing to pay a premium for carbon-neutral products [34,35]. A potential approach to enhance the economic viability is to increase synthesis efficiency, thereby reducing the demand for costly renewable feedstock. To date, integrating a recycle stream has been the best alternative to address this challenge. However, recycling has shown to lead to the buildup of inerts, increased compression demands and equipment size, slow the dynamic response of the system and elevate by-product formation [36]. A potential solution

is to avoid recycling by using novel multi-reactor configurations that are able to increase reactant conversion and thus reduce feedstock requirements even in once-through operation, as was described in previous works by the authors [36].

Shipping fuel regulation and emerging e-fuel mandates are tightening the constraint on acceptable carbon sources, increasing the strategic value of biogenic CO₂ as a renewable-carbon input to e-fuels. However, most biogenic CO₂ is distributed and dilute (e.g., biomass flue gas), meaning that capture-conditioning and power-hydrogen integration, not synthesis chemistry, will determine the practical scalability of e-methanol. This creates a near-term decision problem for ports, developers, and policymakers regarding the time and system conditions that will allow for the bio-CO₂ e-methanol pathway to be established as a credible production pathway.

Despite growing interest in e-methanol, a key unresolved question is whether dilute biogenic CO₂ from distributed biomass combustion facilities can serve as a scalable and deployable carbon source for maritime fuel synthesis, rather than only high-purity CO₂ streams or fossil point sources. Existing studies largely emphasize generic hydrogen-to-methanol routes, fossil CO₂ utilization, or concentrated biogenic CO₂ streams, leaving limited understanding of the capture/conditioning/synthesis integration challenges and competitiveness implications associated with dilute biomass flue gas. To address this gap, the present work provides a gate-to-gate techno-economic framework that links dilute bio-CO₂ capture/conditioning, renewable H₂ supply, and methanol synthesis/purification within a consistent modelling and costing basis. The analysis quantifies the dominant system-level drivers (i.e. electricity price, electrolyser utilization (capacity factor), and electrolyser efficiency) and evaluates how these interact with plant scale and synthesis configuration to define competitiveness thresholds. In this way, the case study functions as a representative anchor to derive broader, transferable competitiveness boundary conditions and a viability window for bio-CO₂-to-methanol pathways, while also enabling deployment-relevant interpretation (e.g., clustering/shared infrastructure) from the observed scale effects. The key novelties and contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- Develops a gate-to-gate TEA framework that consistently integrates dilute bio-CO₂ capture/conditioning, renewable H₂ supply, and methanol synthesis/purification for maritime e-methanol production;
- Uses detailed process simulation to compare synthesis configurations (once-through vs recycle and multi-reactor concepts) and links performance changes to cost impacts;

- Identifies and quantifies system-level drivers (electricity price, electrolyser utilization, electrolyser efficiency) and their interactions as the dominant levers shaping e-MeOH economics;
- Defines competitiveness boundary conditions and a viability window that can be transferred across distributed biomass combustion sources;
- Derives deployment-relevant implications (economies of scale, clustering/shared infrastructure logic) from the cost structure and scale effects.

The remainder of this paper is organized into five sections. Section 2 introduces the key characteristics of the selected biogenic CO₂ facility and provides a detailed description of the examined case study. It also outlines the three core process units of the e-methanol value chain, together with the modelling framework and the main assumptions adopted for feedstock supply and methanol synthesis. Section 3 describes the methodology applied for the techno-economic evaluation. Section 4 presents the results of the analysis, including the economic performance of the simulated cases, a detailed breakdown of methanol production costs, a sensitivity analysis assessing the impact of key process and economic parameters, and an evaluation of potential cost-reduction pathways and feedstock price thresholds required to approach market parity. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the main conclusions of the study and discusses their implications for policy-making and future deployment of maritime e-methanol.

2. Case study overview

The bio-CO₂ to MeOH process encompasses three main sections: bio-CO₂ sourcing, renewable hydrogen production and methanol synthesis. In this study, bio-CO₂ is assumed to be captured from an existing biomass-fired combined heat and power plant that supplies heated water in an extended district heat network through the use of two 15 MW tube boilers. Locally-sourced agricultural residues serve as the primary feedstock, which is combusted to heat water at temperatures exceeding 130 °C. The heated water is then recirculated to over 2000 households before returning at ambient temperature to complete the cycle.

Biomass-combustion facilities are in general characterized by larger capacities (compared to other bio-CO₂ sources); yet their emissions streams are typically diluted containing on average less than 12 vol% CO₂. Such low concentrations prevent its direct use for synthesis and necessitate CO₂ capture methods. This work considers an amine-based capture process using an aqueous monoethanolamine (MEA) solution, which is regarded as the benchmark for post-combustion capture and is widely employed in industrial applications [37]. A key limitation when applying MEA-based capture to flue gases from biomass-combustion processes is the presence of impurities, such as NO_x, SO_x, halogens (HCl, HF), and particulate matter. These impurities must be removed prior to capture as they can degrade the solvent and increase make-up rates [38]. The considered plant already incorporates advanced emission control technologies, including flue gas desulfurization systems (DeSO_x) and ash removal systems. In addition, secondary conditioning stages are assumed to effectively remove any remaining trace impurities. The flue gas composition and properties were determined through a dedicated sampling campaign conducted by the authors and reported in previous work (Table 1) [33].

After capture, the bio-CO₂ stream is directed to the methanol synthesis facility where it is combined with the required green-H₂ supplied by a dedicated water electrolysis facility. It is assumed that bio-CO₂ generation/capture and methanol production are taking place within the combustion plant boundaries. Therefore, technical and economic factors related to the transport of feedstocks to the synthesis facility or of the final methanol product to the point of consumption are not considered. An overview of the investigated case study, including key stream compositions and conditions, is provided in Fig. 1.

The following sections present the three main processes involved in

Table 1

Composition and properties of the flue gas generated by the biomass combustion plant [33].

Parameter	Value
Flow rate, kg/h	49,795
Pressure, bar	1
Temperature, °C	130
Composition in wet basis, mol.%	
CO ₂	11.92
N ₂	70.74
H ₂ O	10.4
CO	0.01
O ₂	6.93

the generation of the required feedstock and the synthesis of the final methanol product, along with the modelling methodology and assumptions used. Indicative stream results regarding the base case conditions can be found in the Appendix.

2.1. CO₂ capture

A simplified layout of the MEA-based CO₂ capture process is shown in Fig. 2. The treated flue gas is first cooled in a direct contact cooler and compressed to offset the small pressure drop in the absorber, which operates near atmospheric pressure at 40–60 °C. Inside the absorber, cooled lean amine (Lean MEA Recycle) is introduced from the top and comes into contact with flue gas fed from the bottom, in a counter current direction [39]. Since MEA poses a health and environmental hazard, the exiting gas passes through a washing section, where water removes MEA carryover to permissible levels [40,41]. The CO₂-rich solvent leaving the bottom is preheated by the hot lean MEA stream exiting the reboiler and pumped to the desorber at 2 bar before being regenerated using steam [42,43]. The reboiler heating demand has been recognized as the primary drawback of the CO₂ capture process, with duties typically ranging from 2.7 to 5.0 MJ_{th} per kilogram of CO₂ captured [21,44], which is consistent with the simulation result of 3.75 MJ_{th}/kg CO₂ for the considered case. At the top of the desorption column, the CO₂-water vapor mixture is partially condensed, allowing CO₂ removal as a gas. Following regeneration, the hot lean MEA solvent is cooled in two stages before being reintroduced into the absorber to complete the process cycle. To compensate for losses occurring from the desorber overhead and the washing section, two makeup streams of water and MEA respectively are introduced into the recycle stream.

The complete capture process is simulated in Aspen PlusTM under steady state conditions. The liquid phase was modeled using the unsymmetric electrolyte NRTL property method (ENRTL-RK), while the vapor phase was described using the PC-SAFT equation of state. In addition, CO₂, N₂ and O₂ were selected as Henry-components to which Henry's law is applied [45]. The full methodology and governing equations associated with these models are implemented within Aspen PlusTM and are documented in the corresponding simulation file [45]. For the simulation of the absorber/desorber columns, the rate-based approach was considered which accounts for mass transfer kinetics, chemical reaction kinetics, and column hydrodynamics, assuming equilibrium only at the interface [39,46–48], whereas the DCC and washing section units were modeled as equilibrium blocks [21,48]. Furthermore, it is assumed that a thorough cleaning of trace impurities and drying process is conducted on the captured bio-CO₂ stream before entering the synthesis section, which is included in the costing procedure. Table 2 presents the properties and composition of the captured stream whereas, the main assumptions and specifications used to model the CO₂ capture process can be found in the Appendix.

2.2. Green Hydrogen production

Green H₂ is produced via electrolysis, where water molecules are

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the bio-CO₂ to methanol case study for the once-through four reactor configuration and baseline conditions.

Fig. 2. Simplified CO₂-MEA capture process diagram.

Table 2
Properties of the captured bio-CO₂ stream.

Parameter	Value
Flow rate, kg/h	8075
Pressure, bar	2
Temperature, °C	25
Composition, mol.%	
CO ₂	99.86
N ₂	0.14

split into hydrogen and oxygen using renewable electricity. Existing technologies, such as alkaline electrolyzers (AEL) and proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzers, are currently the most mature and widely available with both producing hydrogen with purities above 99.9% and are designed for safe, long-term operation [49]. Overall, AEL is the most cost-effective and mature option, however they are subjected to slow start-up, ramp up/down times, and complex equipment [50]. In contrast, PEM electrolysis, while being more capital-expensive, it offers additional advantages such as higher current densities, high energy efficiency, low gas crossover and rapid dynamic response. The latter is especially important in green hydrogen production where the system is connected to a renewable energy source, resulting in variable electricity input that necessitates rapid start-up and shut-down cycles [49,51,52]. Additionally, PEM electrolysis represents more than 65% of the installed electrolysis capacity in Europe, with projections indicating a further

increase in its usage in the following years when production is scaled up [50,52]. Therefore, it is selected as the reference option for this analysis.

Based on the lower heating value of hydrogen, the electrical energy required by the stack to produce 1 kg of H₂ via water electrolysis is 51.1 kWh [53]. Including auxiliary equipment consumption of 4.2 kWh/kgH₂, the total specific electricity demand increases to 55.3 kWh/kgH₂. Another important consideration is the system operating time; the capacity factor represents the ratio of the actual production rate to the maximum possible production rate if the system is operated at full capacity continuously [54]. For systems directly connected with RES, capacity factors could range between 15 and 35% [55]. Direct grid connection can result in higher capacity factors but the environmental performance of hydrogen production is related to the grid mix source [56]. In this study, renewable electricity supply is represented by a power purchase agreement (PPA) assuming grid connection and a fixed electricity price. This connection scheme enables operation at higher capacity factors, which in the base-case is assumed to be 80%. In Table 3 the key parameters and assumptions for the PEM system and H₂ feed stream are presented.

Regarding water consumption, a baseline value of 10 kg H₂O per kg H₂ is assumed for PEM electrolysis [57]. Accounting for an additional 10% water losses due to evaporation and leaks, and 25% excess water for equipment cleaning [57], the final assumed value is 13.5 kg H₂O/kg H₂, which is consistent with values reported in related literature [58]. In addition to hydrogen, electrolyzers produce a pure oxygen stream as a

Table 3Key parameters and assumptions for the PEM system and H₂ feed stream.

Electrolysis system	
Stack efficiency, kWh/kg _{H₂}	51.1
Energy demands for the auxiliary equipment [53], kWh/kg _{H₂}	4.2
H ₂ feed	
Pressure, bar	30
Temperature, °C	25
Composition, mol.%	
H ₂	99.9
H ₂ O	0.1

by-product of the electrolysis reaction with added-value; as rule of thumb for every kg of H₂, 8 kg of O₂ are produced. Oxygen is a critical component in different sectors such as the cement, glass, pulp and paper, wastewater treatment, medical care, ceramics and the iron and steel industry [59]. After its production, oxygen can be conditioned, stored, and sold to the aforementioned industries for additional revenue. It is assumed that the generated O₂ stream is compressed and stored at 150 bar before being sold at an average price of 80 €/t O₂ (as the base-case), to offset part of the hydrogen production costs [23,60,61].

2.3. Methanol synthesis and purification

Fig. 3 depicts the conventional methanol synthesis configuration. In this setup, the fresh CO₂ stream is compressed in four stages with intermediate cooling and then combined with green H₂, which requires a single compression step to reach the reactor operating pressure. The fresh feedstock is then mixed with the recycle stream (if recycling is applied) and is preheated before being directed to the reactor where the exothermic hydrogenation of CO (Eq. 1) and CO₂ (Eq. 2), as well as the Reverse Water Gas Shift (RWGS) reaction (Eq. 3) take place [62]:

It can be seen that combining two of the three reactions forms the remaining one, indicating that there is an interdependency in the reaction system [63]. Methanol formation is favored at low temperatures and high pressures due to its exothermic nature and the resulting reduction in volume [64]. However, reaction kinetics and catalyst limitations result in industrial methanol synthesis typically taking place at 210–280 °C and 50–100 bar [65,66].

Another consideration for MeOH synthesis using CO/CO₂ is the stoichiometric number (S.N.), which refers to the molar ratio between the reactants (Eq. 4).

$$\text{S.N.} = \frac{[\text{H}_2] - [\text{CO}_2]}{[\text{CO}_2] + [\text{CO}]} \quad (4)$$

Where [H₂], [CO₂], and [CO] represent the molar concentration of reactants H₂, CO₂, and CO respectively at the reactor inlet.

Considering the stoichiometry of the hydrogenation reactions, the stoichiometric hydrogen addition is achieved when S.N. is equal to 2. Values below 2 indicate sub-stoichiometric addition of hydrogen (that

reduce conversion but result in higher hydrogen utilization per methanol product), while higher values result in over-stoichiometric hydrogen addition, increasing hydrogen consumption but resulting in lower hydrogen utilization per methanol product [36]. In this work, a S.N. equal to 2 is adopted for all cases, indicating stoichiometric hydrogen addition [19,67].

After reaction, the product gases are cooled and sent to a high-pressure flash drum. The separated crude methanol then undergoes two pressure reductions before a second low-pressure flash drum separates a liquid stream containing methanol, water, and traces of unreacted gases. Crude methanol produced in the reactor can also contain by-products such as ethanol, ketones, esters, C₃+ alcohols, hydrocarbons and others in smaller quantities [68]. In conventional syngas-based methanol plants, by-product concentrations typically reach around 2000 ppm. However, their formation has been shown to be dependent on the concentration of CO in the feed stream, with the results indicating that utilizing a CO₂-rich feed can reduce by-product concentration by up to five times [35,68]. In this work, since the CO₂ feed stream used is nearly pure, focus is placed on the removal of dissolved gases and water to achieve the desired methanol grade.

The crude-MeOH stream is preheated and led to the distillation column, which is equipped with a partial vapor-liquid condenser for light ends separation at the top and a kettle reboiler for heavy ends separation at the bottom, to produce methanol to various specifications. As maritime methanol grade standards are still evolving, the ISO 6583:2024 standard is used as the starting point [69]. The standard provides three distinct grades; MMA-MMB with a maximum water content of 0.1 wt% and minimum dry purity of 99.85 wt% and MMC with a maximum water content of 0.5 wt% and minimum dry purity of 99.7 wt%. While these grades are defined in the context of maritime applications, the resulting products are not exclusive to this sector and may also be suitable for other uses depending on purity requirements. MMA and MMB grades have similar specifications to the established chemical AA grade, which allows their use as a chemical feedstock and thus access higher-value markets providing additional revenue. In contrast the MMC grade is better aligned with energy applications where ultra-high purity is not required.

In this context, the grade of the final maritime fuel directly affects its energy content, and therefore its suitability for fuel use, while also determining the required level of purification and the associated processing costs. Higher water concentrations can reduce purification demands, but also result in a more diluted fuel. Therefore lower purity grades exhibit reduced energy densities, which means ships must either refuel more frequently or carry larger fuel tanks, reducing available storage space. Estimating the fuel energy content based on ISO 6583:2024, the considered grades correspond to 19.83 MJ/kg for MMA-MMB and 19.63 MJ/kg for MMC. This means that high purity grades such as MMA and MMB methanol are the closest in terms of energy content with conventional fuels and therefore the easiest for direct integration to the current maritime fleet. However they require more intense purification and therefore result in increased production costs. Lower-purity grades allow higher water content, simplifying production, but their lower energy density increases the volumes needed to meet the same energy demand, raising storage and transport requirements. Nevertheless, MMC-MeOH represents a practical compromise between product quality and process efficiency, as it reduces the purification requirements while still meeting the necessary specifications for safe handling, storage, and combustion performance. Consequently, it is selected for the following analysis.

Conventional methanol synthesis suffers from equilibrium limitations, which reduce process efficiency and raise feedstock and energy demands. Introducing a recycle stream improves conversion but creates challenges such as inert buildup, higher compression loads, larger equipment, slower dynamic response, and greater by-product formation [36,70]. Multi-reactor, once-through configurations offer an alternative by increasing efficiency without the need for recycling leading to faster

Fig. 3. Flowsheet of the conventional single-reactor MeOH synthesis process.

dynamics and minimum inert component accumulation [24]. In multi-reactor systems, the synthesis loop is divided into several reactors-separators. The gas stream from each high-pressure separator is reheated and sent to the next reactor, with intermediate condensation and product removal between stages. Removing methanol and water improves conversion, shifting thus the reaction toward the methanol and water products and reducing fresh CO₂ and H₂ demands [36] as well as protecting the synthesis catalysts from the formed water [71]. The advantages of the multi-reactor system with intermediate condensation steps has been demonstrated by different authors in previous works [36,67] and the four-reactor methanol synthesis scheme, is illustrated in Fig. 4, both for once-through and recycle operation.

The considered configurations are simulated in Aspen Plus™ under steady state conditions, with the use of Predictive Soave-Redlich-Kwong (PSRK) property package [72]. For the purification section the Non-Random Two Liquid (NRTL) property method package was used, with all non-condensable components treated as Henry components [18,30]. The methanol synthesis reactor was modeled assuming chemical equilibrium, which was determined by minimizing the system's total Gibbs free energy [73]. The main assumptions and specifications used to the model methanol synthesis process can be found in the Appendix.

3. Cost estimation methodology and assumptions

This techno-economic assessment covers CO₂ capture, renewable H₂ supply, and methanol synthesis/purification. The next sections present the methodology for the capital cost estimation (Section 3.1) and the operating costs (Section 3.2).

3.1. Capital cost estimation methodology

This section analyzes the methods and assumptions used to estimate the capital costs of the required facilities, which are defined by the fixed capital investment (FCI) that includes both direct and indirect costs. Direct costs cover the equipment purchase and delivery, installation labor and materials, instrumentation and controls, piping, electrical systems, buildings, yard improvements, and service facilities. Indirect costs include engineering fees, construction expenses, legal costs, and contingencies [74].

To estimate the fixed capital investment for the CO₂ capture and methanol synthesis sections each cost component was represented as a fixed percentage of the total purchased and delivered equipment costs [23,74]. The percentages used mainly depend on the type of process involved and design complexity and are presented in Table 4.

The purchase costs for the major process equipment were estimated using the scaling factor method, in which the cost of each unit is derived from a baseline cost by scaling its characteristic capacity relative to a known reference value through Eq. 5:

$$C_2 = C_1 \cdot \left(\frac{S_2}{S_1}\right)^n \quad (5)$$

Where C_1 is the reference free on board (FOB) cost of equipment with

Table 4
Contribution of each cost item to the fixed capital investment [23,74].

Direct costs	
Purchased and delivered equipment (PDE)	100% of PDE
Equipment installation	40% of PDE
Instrumentation and controls (Installed)	25% of PDE
Piping (installed)	45% of PDE
Electrical systems (installed)	20% of PDE
Building (including services)	10% of PDE
Service facilities and yard improvements	30% of PDE
Total direct costs (TDC)	Sum of direct costs
Indirect costs	
Engineering and supervision	18% of DC
Construction and contractor expenses	15% of DC
Legal expenses	2% of DC
Contingency	8% of DC
Total indirect costs (TIC)	Sum of indirect costs
Fixed capital investment (FCI)	TDC + TIC

capacity equal to S_1 , C_2 is the FOB cost of the desired equipment with capacity equal to S_2 and n is a scaling factor which depends on the type of equipment and capacity range. The reference equipment cost data utilized can be seen in Table 5 and an additional 10% of the purchase cost was added to account for delivery [74,75].

In the case of the PEM electrolyser, the fixed capital investment was estimated using a bottom-up approach based on the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) manufacturing cost analysis [53]. Stack and balance-of-plant cost data for 1 MW systems, reported for an annual manufacturing capacity of 100 MW and summarized in Table 5, were scaled to the required electrolyser capacity using the scale factors reported in [23]. In cases where a scaling factor for a specific component was not available, the base value of 0.6 was used, in line with the typically used six-tenths rule in process equipment cost scaling [74]. Manufacturer markup, taken as 50% of manufacturing costs, and installation costs, assumed as 33% of purchase costs, were then added to obtain the total installed cost [80]. Stack replacement is assumed to occur once the 70,000 h lifetime is reached, with the replacement costs equal to 15% of the total installed costs [53,81]. Additional indirect costs were included as fixed fractions of the installed cost, accounting for site preparation (2%), engineering-design (10%), and contingencies (15%) [53,82]. This results in the final total capital investment for the electrolyser unit amounting to approximately 1000 €/kW, which is consistent with the KPIs reported by the Clean Hydrogen JU [83].

Following the estimation of FCI for the considered process sections, another 10% of the FCI is included to account for the working capital investment (WCI) which is required for the initial plant operations [74]. The final total capital investment (TCI) results from the sum of FCI and WCI. In addition, the total production cost of methanol is estimated and used as an economic benchmark. This enables the identification of the main cost drivers, through a detailed cost breakdown, and comparison between the considered cases. For the calculation of TPC, TCI is considered a one-time expense and is distributed across the lifetime of the project through the utilization of the capital recovery factor. The

Fig. 4. Flowsheet of the multi-reactor synthesis section.

Table 5
Reference cost data and scaling factors for the considered equipment.

Equipment	Scaling unit	Reference year	Base size	Scale factor	Reference cost, USD	Reference
CO ₂ capture-Methanol synthesis section						
Blower	Flow rate, Nm ³ /h		30	0.61	760,000	
Pump	Drive power, kW		23	0.29	9500	
Pressure vessels and absorber-desorber shell	Volume, m ³		20	0.52	100,000	
Heat exchanger and condenser-reboiler	Heat transfer area, m ²	2007	100	0.71	70,000	[76]
Compressor	Drive power, kW		1000	0.9	1,350,000	
Distillation column	(Height, m)·(Diameter, m) ^{1.5}		65	0.9	1,425,000	
Structured packing for Absorber-Desorber	USD/m ³	2010	1	1	2000	[77]
MeOH reactor	t/h	2001	87.5	0.62	7,000,000	[23]
PEM electrolysis						
Electrolyser stack	USD/kW	2020	1 MW	0.89	183	
Hydrogen processing	USD/kW	2020	1 MW	0.6	111	
Hydrogen-side BOP	USD/kW	2020	1 MW	0.6	5	
Piping, instrumentation, housing	USD/kW	2020	1 MW	0.6	105	[23,53]
Electrical BOP	USD/kW	2020	1 MW	0.75	175	
Water supply	USD/kW	2020	1 MW	0.73	56	
Thermal management	USD/kW	2020	1 MW	0.73	70	
Storage tank*	O ₂	2008	70	0.86	100,000	[23]
	H ₂	2017	227	0.44	300,321	[78]
	CO ₂	2018	2	0.6	17,000	[79]

* To accommodate short-term fluctuations, intermediate buffer storage tanks are included and sized to provide 6 h of storage capacity.

total production cost of methanol is calculated through Eq. 6:

$$TPC = \frac{TCI \bullet CRF + OPEX}{\dot{m}MeOH} \quad (6)$$

Where *TPC* is the total production cost of methanol in €/kg_{MeOH}, *TCI·CRF* represents the annualized total capital expenses in €/year, *OPEX* is the total operational expenses in €/year and *ṁMeOH* is the total mass flow rate of the produced methanol in kg_{MeOH}/year.

The complete set of economic assumptions made is presented in Table 6.

To ensure comparability, all cost estimates are updated to a common reference year (2024) and currency. For this reason the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index (CECPI) is used along with the USD to Euro exchange factor (0.92 USD/€ as an average value for 2024) [84].

3.2. Operational cost estimation methodology

Operational expenses are calculated on an annual basis and include all costs associated with plant operation. These include variable costs such as labor, utilities, maintenance and repairs, consumables, and catalysts or solvents, as well as fixed charges covering taxes, insurance, and plant overhead and administration expenses [74]. All of the above costs are considered and the data used along with the assumption made to estimate them are presented in Table 7.

For the electrolysis facility, the main operational costs, apart from utilities, are fixed operating and maintenance costs. These include operating labor, maintenance, and overhead, and are assumed to be equal to 5% of the total installed electrolyser cost [89].

4. Results

The following sections present the economic evaluation and results of the investigated cases. Section 4.1 applies the cost estimation methodology to determine the total production costs of methanol for the two considered synthesis configurations. Moreover, a cost breakdown is

Table 6
Assumptions for the economic evaluation.

Variable	Value
Project lifetime, years	20
Days of operation, days/year	330
Interest rate, %	8
Capital recovery factor	0.10

Table 7
Operational costs estimation data and assumptions.

Cost component	Base value	Reference
Operating labor, €/h	33.5	[74,85]
Operating supervision	15% of operating labor	[74]
Electricity, €/MWh	50 ^a	[86,87]
Cooling water, €/t	0.15	[74]
Process water, €/t	0.99	[74]
Utilities		
Low pressure steam, €/t	3.7	
Medium pressure steam, ^b €/t	8	[74]
High pressure steam, €/t	11.5	
Wastewater processing, €/t	0.99	[74]
Maintenance and repairs	2% of FCI	[74]
Operating supplies	15% of maintenance and repairs	[74]
Catalysts- MeOH synthesis catalyst, €/t	17,700	[67]
Solvents MEA, €/kg	1.34	[88]
Fixed	1% of FCI	[74]
Plant overhead	60% of operating labor, supervision, maintenance and repairs	[74]
Administrative expenses	15% of operating labor	[74]
H ₂	1.5% of H ₂ storage CAPEX	[79,83]
CO ₂ , €/m ³	3.5% of CO ₂ storage CAPEX	[19,79]
Storage	Based on the power demands to compress oxygen from 30 to 150 bar	
O ₂ , €/kg		

^a The selected electricity price is based on the reported range of levelized costs of renewable electricity, as reported by IRENA for 2024 [99], and is consistent with assumptions used in comparable e-MeOH techno-economic studies [18].

^b It is assumed that 50% of the desorption and distillation heating demand is supplied via CHP-based heat integration, a conservative estimate given its demonstrated potential to substantially reduce external heating in similar plants [15].

provided to identify the contribution of each component on the TPC. In Section 4.2 a sensitivity analysis is conducted to assess the effect of variations and uncertainties in key assumptions of the production costs. Based on these results, Section 4.3 presents possible pathways for reducing production costs: Section 4.3.1 explores how economies of scale can reduce costs, while Section 4.3.2 investigates the effect of

alternative electricity price scenarios and electrolyser capacity factors. Finally, in Section 4.3.3, an overall assessment of the required cost reductions for e-MeOH to achieve economic competitiveness is conducted, along with a discussion of potential approaches to reach these targets. Overall, to translate plant-level results into deployment-relevant insights, the analysis is structured around a scenario space spanning different electricity prices (30–150 €/MWh), electrolyser capacity factors (20–90%), plant scales (<2000 tpd MeOH), and oxygen credits. These scenarios represent potential deployment archetypes: direct RES coupling (low electricity price but low capacity factor), grid/PPA operation (higher capacity factor with more stable output) as well as clustered scale-up via shared CO₂ conditioning and hydrogen infrastructure.

4.1. Methanol production costs

The results of the economic assessment, presented in Fig. 5, show that implementing the four-reactor once-through setup results in a TPC of 1.43€/kg, which is significantly higher than the 2024 bunker price for grey methanol at the port of Rotterdam (0.30–0.47 €/kg) [90]. Operating in a recycle loop helps reduce this gap with the TPC reaching 1.10 €/kg. Although recycling results in a 13% increase in the MeOH synthesis TCI due to the larger equipment demands, it also results in a 23% increase on MeOH yield ultimately lowering the specific production cost. Further cost reductions are possible through the valorization of by-product oxygen which decreases the TPC to 1.25 €/kg and 0.96 €/kg for the once-through and recycle operations, respectively. However, due to the operational drawbacks associated with recycling, such as inert buildup and reduced dynamic flexibility, the once-through setup is selected for the subsequent analysis.

A cost breakdown for the four-reactor once-through configuration shows that green hydrogen production is the main cost contributor, accounting for 73.7% of the TPC. This is primarily attributed to the power demands of electrolysis (52.3% of the TPC) and the significant capital expenses of the electrolyser unit, which represent 65.8% of the total CAPEX and 16.5% of the TPC. Other electrolysis-related expenditures, including water feedstock, H₂ and O₂ storage, and fixed operational costs, contribute an additional 4.9% to the TPC. The methanol synthesis section represents the second-largest cost segment at 18.4% of the TPC. This is divided into 6.6% from CAPEX and 11.8% from OPEX, with the primary drivers being compression requirements (2.3%) and the synthesis reactors and high-pressure vessels (4.8%). Finally, the bio-CO₂ capture segment is the least capital-intensive component, contributing only 7.9% to the TPC, with 5.9% associated with operational costs and 2% with capital expenses. Overall, given the dominance of H₂-related OPEX, the following sensitivity analysis shows which system variables can realistically reduce hydrogen-driven and in consequence methanol production costs.

4.2. Sensitivity analysis

Section 4.1 showed that the total production cost of e-methanol depends on several factors, many of which are uncertain and/or are expected to evolve over time. For this reason, a sensitivity analysis is conducted on selected base-case parameters with the main findings presented in Fig. 6.

The findings indicate that a reduction of the interest rate to 4% can have a significant impact, with the TPC decreasing by 8%. Such reduction can be a result of the lower risk involved driven by favorable regulatory conditions and technology improvements as e-MeOH facilities move toward the Nth-of-a-Kind (NOAK) status. In contrast, an increase of the interest rate to 12%, due to market uncertainty or limited policy support, results in a 9% increase of TPC. Process CAPEX is also a significant factor: a $\pm 40\%$ change in total CAPEX results in an approximately $\pm 15\%$ variation in methanol TPC, with the electrolysis CAPEX contributing mostly to this outcome ($\pm 9.5\%$). This is particularly relevant as electrolyser CAPEX is expected to decline in coming years due to larger deployment volumes enabling economies of scale, technological improvements, and large-scale manufacturing, especially for balance-of-plant components [53]. Similar variations on the other OPEX (labor, plant overhead, maintenance and repairs, administrative, operating supplies and fixed costs) and non-electricity utilities prices sections results in a $\pm 8.1\%$ and $\pm 1.7\%$ deviation respectively. Finally, a $\pm 40\%$ variation on the oxygen selling price could exhibit a $\pm 5.5\%$ variance on the total production cost of methanol.

Considering the significant influence of the electrolyser capital costs to the TPC, Fig. 7 illustrates the relative change in the TPC compared to the base-case value as a function of the electrolyser's CAPEX. The examined range of 500–2000 €/kW reflects both current market values and expected future cost-reduction projections [83,91,92]. Notably, the findings show that doubling the electrolyser CAPEX from the base case value of approximately 1000 €/kW to 2000 €/kW results in a 21% increase in TPC, corresponding to a total production cost of 1.52 €/kg. Conversely, a reduction to 500 €/kW results in a 10% decrease relative to the base case (1.13 €/kg). This points to the significant role that continued electrolyser cost reductions will play in improving the economic competitiveness of large-scale e-MeOH production. Such cost reductions could be feasible in the future based on the projected trend of development for electrolyser technologies. For example, recent assessments by the IEA indicate that despite an increase in installed electrolyser CAPEX in the past years due to higher material and labour costs, further technology development and scale-up are expected to reverse this trend. In particular, higher production rates are projected to lower costs through economies of scale, with a strong effect on balance-of-plant components, with electrolyser CAPEX falling below 600 €/kW by 2030 [91]. Similarly, IRENA reports a consistent downward trend, driven by technological progress at stack level, improved system

Fig. 5. Total production cost and cost component breakdown for the four-reactor once-through and recycle configurations.

Fig. 6. Sensitivity of the total methanol production cost to variations in the interest rate, CAPEX, other OPEX, utility prices (excluding electricity), and O₂ selling price.

Fig. 7. Effect of electrolyser CAPEX on the relative total production cost of methanol compared with the base value.

integration, and large-scale deployment [92]. These projections are further supported by the Clean Hydrogen JU also setting progressively low KPIs, reaching 500 €/kW in 2030 [83].

4.3. Cost-reduction pathways and e-MeOH competitiveness

Sections 4.1 and 4.2 showed that costs linked to green hydrogen production dominate the economics of e-methanol. Section 4.3 evaluates cost-reduction levers in a deployment-relevant manner by translating plant-level results into system-level boundary conditions. Specifically, we quantify how economies of scale, electricity procurement, and electrolyser utilization determine the achievable e-MeOH cost range and therefore define a viability window for bio-CO₂-to-methanol pathways. This framing enables interpretation beyond the specific case plant by identifying which variables remain site-dependent (e.g., flue-gas flow and composition) and which dominate across sites (electricity price and electrolyser capacity factor).

4.3.1. Effect of economies of scale

The reference biomass-based CHP facility, with a capacity of 30 MW_{th}, represents the lower end of the EU biomass-CHP plants, which typically ranges from 3.5 to 200 MW_{th} [93]. Given that capital expenditures exhibit non-linear scaling with capacity, larger facilities can

exploit economies of scale and reduce specific costs. This potential becomes especially interesting in the case of CO₂ cluster-hub projects in which multiple emitters are aggregated into a shared CO₂ hub enabling the utilization of higher capacities than autonomous projects [94]. The beneficial impact of economies-of-scale has been also outlined and investigated in previous methanol synthesis-related works [95–97]. To assess the impact of scale, the flue gas flow rate was varied between 10 and 1000 t/h, corresponding to methanol production capacities of approximately 20–2000 t/day. Data from the reference CHP plant, including flue gas composition, operating conditions, flow rate, and economic parameters, served as the basis for scaling. Fig. 8 illustrates the relative change in the TPC compared to the base-case value as a function of production capacity.

The results show that the most significant economic benefits are achieved during the transition from small (<100 t/day) to medium-scale (>500 t/day) facilities, whereas there are diminishing cost-reduction effects beyond that scale. In particular, operation at a small-scale capacity of 20 t/day increases the TPC by 67%, from 1.25 €/kg to 2.10 €/kg, compared with the baseline case (≈100 t/day). In contrast, doubling the production rate to 200 t/day yields a reduction of only 9% (to 1.15 €/kg), while at ten times the base capacity (1000 t/day) the TPC is reduced to 0.96 €/kg yielding only a 24% reduction. At capacities exceeding 1000 t/day, the cost curve approaches a plateau of

Fig. 8. Effect of plant production capacity on the relative total production cost of methanol compared with the base value.

approximately 0.91 €/kg. At these scales, operational costs, particularly the electricity for hydrogen production, dominate the TPC and prevent further significant cost reductions. It is important to mention that even at large-scale production rates of 2000 t/day range, the production cost remains substantially higher than the 2024 grey methanol bunkering price range of 0.30–0.47 €/kg reported for the Port of Rotterdam [90].

4.3.2. Effect of electricity price and capacity factor

While economies of scale reduce specific costs when moving from small to medium-scale plants, they do not alter the fact that e-MeOH TPC is dominated by operating expenses which scale linearly. In particular, electricity-related costs for green-H₂ generation contribute approximately 33–70% of the total TPC across the investigated scales, making electricity price the single most important external driver of e-MeOH economics. This dependency is particularly significant given the continuous fluctuations in the electricity market, resulting in the price of electricity being one of the most uncertain variables in such a project [98]. Electricity price and electrolyser capacity factor are coupled in practice through procurement strategy: direct coupling to variable renewables may reduce average electricity costs but typically lowers utilization, whereas grid connection and/or PPAs can raise utilization at higher electricity prices. As a result, competitiveness is governed not only by the level of electricity prices but also by the achievable operating hours and the resulting required installed electrolyser capacity.

Therefore, a dedicated assessment was performed considering only

variations in electricity price while all other cost assumptions were kept constant. To provide a realistic assessment, the selected range (30–150 €/MWh) encompasses the lowest levelized cost of electricity from different renewable generation technologies, as reported by IRENA for 2024, up to the average EU grid electricity price for non-household consumers with annual consumption exceeding 150,000 MWh, based on Eurostat 2024 data [87,99]. The resulting TPC estimations, shown in Fig. 9, indicate that even when low-cost renewable electricity is used (30 €/MWh), methanol production costs remain well above current market prices at 1.12 €/kg (0.95 €/kg with O₂ revenue). Increasing the electricity price from the base case of 50 €/MWh to the grid electricity range of 100–150 €/MWh causes the costs to rise sharply, reaching 2.19–2.95 €/kg, confirming that electricity price alone can shift the process from “high-cost” to “prohibitive-cost” operation ranges.

The price of electricity is directly influenced by the electrolyser’s renewable electricity supply strategy. Direct RES coupling reduces electricity costs but lowers the capacity factor, necessitating electrolyser oversizing and increasing capital investment [100]. Conversely, grid connection allows the electrolyser to operate for more hours per year, but it is also associated with higher electricity prices. Fig. 10 presents an evaluation of these trade-offs by calculating the total production cost of e-MeOH across varying capacity factors and electricity prices.

Higher capacity factors significantly reduce production costs, as the same hydrogen output can be achieved with smaller electrolyser

Fig. 9. Effect of electricity price variation on the total production cost of methanol.

Fig. 10. Total product cost of e-MeOH as a function of the electrolyser capacity factor for different electricity prices.

capacities, which can be enabled through grid connection combined with dedicated renewable electricity PPAs. For example, at an electricity price of 150 €/MWh, increasing the capacity factor from 15% to 90% lowers the TPC by approximately 20.4%. The relative benefit grows as electricity becomes cheaper; reductions reach 34.9% at 50 €/MWh and up to 40.5% at 30 €/MWh. This is because, at lower electricity price points CAPEX represents a larger fraction of the TPC, making high utilization and the associated downsizing of the electrolysis unit more significant. For systems with direct RES connection, a potential approach to increase the capacity factor is to pair the electrolyser with dedicated battery storage. Storage can smooth short-term fluctuations in renewable output and increase the number of operating hours. However, it has been shown that the added capital cost of battery systems could exceed the benefit of higher capacity factors and results in increased hydrogen production costs [101] and therefore requiring optimum sizing and operation scheduling.

4.3.3. E-Methanol competitiveness

The previous sections showed that, even with the implementation of multi-reactor synthesis schemes, increased production scales, and alternative electrolyser power-connection strategies, the total production cost of maritime e-methanol remains higher than fossil-based methanol. This result is primarily driven by the high cost of renewable hydrogen generation which dominates the overall economics of e-MeOH.

To quantify the cost reductions required for e-MeOH to approach economic competitiveness, an analysis similar to that proposed by Rahmat et al. [18] is conducted. In this analysis, the base-case assumptions were identical to those of the investigated case study, while different cost values for CO₂ and green H₂ production were applied. The considered costs were based on the upper limits of cost ranges for CO₂ capture from diluted sources and electrolytically produced green H₂, together with lower-cost scenarios, to identify the reductions required for e-methanol to become competitive [18,102]. Based on the results, three cost-range scenarios are defined to categorize the economic outlook of maritime e-methanol relative to the average bunker price of fossil methanol (0.35 €/kg_{MeOH}):

- Baseline scenario (>1.05 €/kg): Represents production costs that exhibit a price premium exceeding 200% of the fossil benchmark, consistent with current cost levels under existing market conditions.
- Transitional scenario (0.53–1.05 €/kg): The stage in which technological advancements and the deployment of NOAK facilities reduce costs narrowing the price premium to between 50 and 200% relative to grey methanol.
- Target scenario (<0.53 €/kg): Represents the state of market parity, where production costs are reduced to within 50% of the grey-methanol price. At this level, e-methanol is considered

economically competitive, particularly when accounting for projected carbon taxes and market incentives.

The resulted TPCs, presented in Fig. 11, indicate that for most combinations of CO₂ and green-H₂ procurement costs considered, e-MeOH production remains within the baseline cost-range. However, under scenarios where green hydrogen is available at costs below 3 €/kg_{H₂}, the product approaches the transitional cost-range, achieving the target cost limit requires green-H₂ costs below 1 €/kg_{H₂} combined with CO₂ costs below 70 €/t_{CO₂}. At present, such hydrogen cost levels remain unattainable with commercially available dedicated electrolysis facilities. Assuming all other cost components associated with the electrolyser remain unchanged from the base-case scenario, achieving green-H₂ costs below 3 €/kg_{H₂} would require renewable electricity prices <20 €/MWh, which is not feasible under the current status of renewable energy production.

One potential pathway to reduce green-H₂ costs is the integration of the synthesis plant within dedicated hydrogen production hubs, commonly referred to as hydrogen valleys. A hydrogen valley is a geographically defined ecosystem that integrates the entire hydrogen value chain, from production and storage to distribution and end-use application, within a single coordinated framework [103]. The overarching objective of such systems is to supply multiple end-users, thus exploiting economies of scale and significantly reducing logistical and energy losses across the hydrogen value chain [56,104]. Currently, the Clean Hydrogen Partnership reports that the majority of H₂-valleys are producing green-H₂ at a price range of 4–6 €/kg_{H₂}, with only a couple of large-scale projects capable of achieving production prices below 4 €/kg_{H₂} and a single project <2 €/kg_{H₂} [105].

A similar approach can be implemented to reduce CO₂ capture costs by integrating the facility into a CO₂ clustering network in which multiple biogenic CO₂ emitters are aggregated into a cluster where their combined output is collected, pre-conditioned, and transported to the synthesis facility [94]. Combining flue gases from multiple emitters could reduce costs and risks, removing the interdependency between the size of the individual emitters, their investment decision, and the scale of the related storage-transport development [106]. For example, Subraveti et al. [107] showed that clustering multiple emission sources in a single CO₂-MEA capture facility can yield investment savings of up to 10% for two sources, with larger reductions as more sources are added.

Apart from production costs, the deployment of e-MeOH as a maritime fuel entails additional logistics and end-use considerations. Methanol's lower volumetric energy density relative to typical fossil-fuel options implies larger storage-transport requirements and more frequent bunkering, partially offsetting its cost competitiveness even as production costs decline. A more detailed cost assessment would also need to account for the logistics chain, including the distribution to the destination port, which heavily depends on the transportation mode and

Green hydrogen cost, €/kg

CO ₂ feedstock cost, €/t	Green hydrogen cost, €/kg													
	0.5	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5	5.5	6	6.5	7
10	0.42	0.55	0.69	0.82	0.96	1.09	1.23	1.36	1.50	1.63	1.77	1.90	2.04	2.17
20	0.44	0.57	0.71	0.84	0.98	1.11	1.25	1.38	1.52	1.65	1.79	1.92	2.06	2.19
30	0.46	0.59	0.73	0.86	1.00	1.13	1.27	1.40	1.54	1.67	1.81	1.94	2.08	2.21
40	0.48	0.61	0.75	0.88	1.02	1.15	1.29	1.42	1.56	1.69	1.82	1.96	2.09	2.23
50	0.50	0.63	0.77	0.90	1.04	1.17	1.30	1.44	1.57	1.71	1.84	1.98	2.11	2.25
60	0.51	0.65	0.78	0.92	1.05	1.19	1.32	1.46	1.59	1.73	1.86	2.00	2.13	2.27
70	0.53	0.67	0.80	0.94	1.07	1.21	1.34	1.48	1.61	1.75	1.88	2.02	2.15	2.29
80	0.55	0.69	0.82	0.96	1.09	1.23	1.36	1.50	1.63	1.77	1.90	2.04	2.17	2.31
90	0.57	0.71	0.84	0.98	1.11	1.25	1.38	1.52	1.65	1.79	1.92	2.06	2.19	2.33
100	0.59	0.73	0.86	1.00	1.13	1.27	1.40	1.54	1.67	1.81	1.94	2.08	2.21	2.35
110	0.61	0.75	0.88	1.02	1.15	1.29	1.42	1.56	1.69	1.83	1.96	2.10	2.23	2.37
120	0.63	0.77	0.90	1.04	1.17	1.31	1.44	1.58	1.71	1.85	1.98	2.12	2.25	2.39

Target cost-range	<0.53 €/kg _{MeOH}	<50% excess of grey-MeOH price
Transitional cost-range	0.53-1.05 €/kg _{MeOH}	50-200% excess of grey-MeOH price
Baseline cost-range	>1.05 €/kg _{MeOH}	>200% excess of grey-MeOH price

Fig. 11. Total production cost of e-methanol in €/kg_{MeOH} under different green-H₂ and CO₂ capture costs compared with the average grey MeOH bunker price (0.35 €/kg_{MeOH}).

distance. For example, truck transport is typically the most expensive option due to limited carrying capacity, with costs in the range of 1.5–28 €/t [108,109]. Additional bunkering costs, depending on the delivery method (e.g. barge or truck), are reported at 2–6 €/t [110]. When compared to the estimated e-MeOH production costs in this work, the distribution and bunkering expenses would correspond to approximately <1–6% of the TPC, depending on the process configuration. Additionally, current maritime grades set high purity specifications meaning that the produced methanol could also be used as chemical feedstock as well as for the production of a variety of products including sustainable aviation fuels [111]. Compared to these approaches, the maritime sector presents a relatively concentrated demand market centered on major ports, which can facilitate infrastructure rollout and reduce logistics costs at scale. Nevertheless, it should be noted that a detailed assessment of additional logistics and supply chain cost-considerations was outside the scope of the present work.

An additional consideration in maritime e-methanol economics are the policy incentives that could promote the use of RFNBOs and contribute to narrowing the current cost gap. In October 2023, the EU ETS was extended to include CO₂ emissions from all large ships [2], while the FuelEU Maritime regulation imposes GHG intensity reduction targets for all ships above 5000 gross tonnage calling at European ports [6], with a sub-target of at least 2% RFNBOs by 2034. Together, these regulations mean that ship owners continuing under a business-as-usual scenario will face increasing cost penalties, with the effective cost of very low sulphur fuel oil (VLSFO) projected to quadruple by 2050 [112]. At the global level, the IMO net-zero framework establishes two GHG reduction tiers with penalties of 100–380 USD/tCO₂eq for non-compliant vessels [113]. While these policies do not directly reduce e-fuel production costs, they improve the financial viability of RFNBO-based alternatives by reducing the market cost-gap. On the supply side, carbon contracts for difference can further reduce the minimum fuel selling price by providing revenue streams to plant operators, bridging the gap between carbon market prices and a predetermined reference value [114].

However, for e-MeOH to qualify as a viable switching option, it must deliver significant emissions reductions across its entire value chain. Several studies have evaluated the lifecycle emissions of e-MeOH in maritime applications [115–117], indicating that performance is primarily driven by the carbon intensity of electricity for hydrogen production and auxiliary processes and the energy used for carbon capture. More specifically, well-to-wake emissions are estimated at 16–26 gCO₂eq/MJ, with the lower bound corresponding to fully renewable operation and the upper bound reflecting cases where carbon capture

and auxiliary processes rely on natural gas and grid electricity [116]. These values correspond to reductions of 70–80% compared to VLSFO (~90 gCO₂eq/MJ) and enable e-MeOH to meet current and anticipated policy targets.

Overall, these results define transferable competitiveness boundary conditions: bio-CO₂ availability alone is insufficient, and commercial viability depends on simultaneous access to low-cost electricity, high electrolyser utilization, and infrastructure that enables carbon-hydrogen coupling at scale. From a deployment perspective, the cost outcomes reflect recurring implementation modes that can be combined: on-site renewable coupling can reduce average electricity cost but often limits electrolyser capacity factor, increasing required installed capacity and capital charges; grid connection and/or renewable PPAs enable higher utilization and steadier hydrogen output, typically at higher electricity prices and greater OPEX exposure to market volatility; and clustered bio-CO₂ hubs aggregate multiple distributed biomass emitters into shared CO₂ conditioning and synthesis infrastructure, improving scale benefits and reducing duplication of fixed costs. Hydrogen valleys can enable these configurations by coordinating production, storage, distribution and multiple end-uses to increase utilization and reduce unit costs, supporting movement toward the hydrogen-cost ranges required for the “future competitiveness” region identified in Section 4.3.3. Results should be interpreted as scenario-based ranges because electricity price variability and electrolyser operating strategy dominate outcomes. The co-location assumption provides a lower-bound cost; non-co-located systems would require additional CO₂/H₂ compression, transport and storage. Finally, flue-gas impurity profiles and conditioning needs may vary across biomass feedstocks, potentially shifting capture OPEX, although the overall cost hierarchy is expected to remain dominated by hydrogen-related costs.

5. Conclusions

This study assessed the techno-economic feasibility of producing maritime e-methanol from CO₂ captured at a biomass-fired CHP plant and renewable hydrogen from electrolysis, integrating CO₂ capture/conditioning, H₂ supply, and methanol synthesis within a gate-to-gate boundary. The resulting e-methanol production costs remain above current fossil methanol bunker prices, with total production costs of 1.43 €/kg_{MeOH} for the once-through configuration and 1.10 €/kg_{MeOH} for recycle operation; valorization of by-product oxygen can further reduce costs to 1.25 €/kg_{MeOH} and 0.96 €/kg_{MeOH}, respectively. A central finding is that the dominant bottleneck is not methanol synthesis itself but renewable hydrogen affordability and utilization. Electricity

price and electrolyser operating strategy govern the cost outcome, while changes in synthesis configuration mainly affect costs through conversion and feedstock demand. Economies of scale reduce unit costs, particularly from small to mid-scale capacities, but diminishing returns at larger scales indicate that scale-up alone cannot close the gap to fossil methanol as long as electricity-driven hydrogen OPEX remains dominant.

Through the linking of the cost outcomes to electricity price, electrolyser capacity factor, and scale, the analysis defined transferable competitiveness boundary conditions: bio-CO₂ availability alone is insufficient, and viability depends on simultaneous access to low-cost electricity, high electrolyser utilization, and infrastructure that enables carbon-hydrogen coupling at scale. In deployment terms, low-cost on-site renewable coupling can reduce electricity cost but often limits electrolyser utilization; grid/PPA operation increases utilization but may raise electricity costs and OPEX exposure; and clustered bio-CO₂ hubs reduce fixed-cost duplication via shared conditioning and synthesis infrastructure. Hydrogen valleys can enable these configurations by coordinating production, storage, distribution and multiple end-uses, increasing utilization and reducing unit costs toward the hydrogen cost levels required for future competitiveness. Finally, results should be interpreted as scenario-based ranges: electricity price volatility and electrolyser operation dominate outcomes, while assumptions on co-location provide a lower-bound cost relative to distributed supply chains that require additional CO₂/H₂ compression, transport and storage. Overall, the findings position biomass combustion plants as potential distributed renewable-carbon nodes for maritime e-fuel supply chains, but indicate that commercialization hinges primarily on power and hydrogen system integration rather than incremental improvements in methanol synthesis alone.

Declaration of competing interest

Appendix A. Appendix

A.1. Indicative stream results

Indicative stream results obtained from the simulation for the single-reactor and four-reactor once-through configurations under base-case conditions are presented in Table A1 and Table A2 respectively.

Table A1

Main stream results for the examined once-through four-reactor synthesis scheme under base-case conditions.

Stream name	Bio-CO ₂	Green H ₂	Reactor inlet	Crude MeOH	MeOH product
Total mass flow rate (kg/h)	8075	1118	9193	7007	4142
T, K	298	298	483	308	298
P, bar	2	30	70	70	1
% mol fraction					
CO ₂	99.86	–	24.97	3.04	0.22
CO	–	–	–	0.02	–
H ₂ O	–	0.01	0.07	48.96	0.89
H ₂	–	99.9	74.92	0.71	–
N ₂	0.14	–	0.04	–	–
CH ₃ OH	–	–	–	47.26	98.9

Table A2

Main stream results for the examined four-reactor synthesis scheme under 90% recycle conditions.

Stream name	Bio-CO ₂	Green H ₂	Reactor inlet	Crude MeOH	MeOH product
Total mass flow rate (kg/h)	8075	1064	11,687	8856	5287
T, K	298	298	483	308	298
P, bar	2	30	70	70	1
% mol fraction					
CO ₂	99.86	–	24.56	3.08	0.22
CO	–	–	0.44	0.02	–
H ₂ O	–	0.01	0.08	48.25	0.89

(continued on next page)

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was conducted as part of the “M²ARE” project, which is supported and funded by European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement number 101136080. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union and cannot be held responsible for them.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

V. Mitrousis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **E. Koliamitra:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **M. Bampaou:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation. **K.D. Panopoulos:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Table A2 (continued)

Stream name	Bio-CO ₂	Green H ₂	Reactor inlet	Crude MeOH	MeOH product
H ₂	–	99.9	74.58	0.72	–
N ₂	0.14	–	0.26	–	–
CH ₃ OH	–	–	0.09	47.93	98.9

A.2. Modelling assumptions

The parameters and assumptions used to model the CO₂-MEA capture process and the methanol synthesis process are presented in [Table A3](#) and [Table A4](#) respectively.

Table A3

Specifications and assumptions used in the simulation of the CO₂-MEA capture process.

Parameter	Absorber	Desorber
Number of segments	30	30
Operating pressure, bar	1.1 (0.1 bar pressure drop)	2 (isobaric)
Packing type	Mellapak 250Y	Mellapak 250Y
Mass transfer coefficient method [118]	Bravo et al. (1985)	Bravo et al. (1985)
Interfacial area method [118]	Chilton and Colburn	Chilton and Colburn
Heat transfer coefficient method [119]	Bravo et al. (1992)	Bravo et al. (1992)
Holdup correlation [120]	Discrxn for liquid film (5 segments)	Discrxn for liquid film (5 segments)
Film resistance	Consider film for gas phase	Consider film for gas phase
Bulk phase flow model	Mixed	Mixed
Lean loading, molCO ₂ /molMEA		0.25
Heat exchanger temperature approach on the hot side, °C	Lean-Rich Heat Exchanger	15
	Direct Contact Cooler	
Number of equilibrium stages		10
Operating pressure, bar		1 (isobaric)
	Washing section	
Number of equilibrium stages		2
Operating pressure, bar		1 (isobaric)
Capture efficiency %		$\frac{CO_{2,in} - CO_{2,out}}{CO_{2,in}} \bullet 100\% = 90\%$

Table A4

Specifications and assumptions for the simulation of MeOH synthesis.

Pretreatment section	
Compression steps	4 (CO ₂), 1 (H ₂)
Intermediate cooling temperature, °C	35
Synthesis section	
Feed preheating temperature, °C	210
Reaction Temperature, °C	250
Reaction pressure, bar	70
High pressure flash, bar	70
Purification section	
Low pressure flash, bar	1.2
Pre heating temperature, °C	80
Distillation column stage number	15
Feed inlet stage	11
Distillation column pressure, bar	1
MeOH recovery, %	99

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] European Maritime Safety Agency, Discover the EU Maritime Profile. <https://www.emsa.europa.eu/eumaritimeprofile.html>, 2026 (accessed January 28, 2026).
- [2] European Commission, Reducing Emissions from the Shipping Sector. https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/transport/reducing-emissions-shipping-sector_en, 2026.
- [3] J. Mohammadpour, F. Salehi, A review of alternative liquid fuels in marine engines, *Appl. Energy Combust. Sci.* 24 (2025) 100394, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaecs.2025.100394>.
- [4] I. Bellos, IMO Postpones Shipping Global Net Zero Framework for One Year. <https://www.ekathimerini.com/news/environment/1284136/imo-delays-postpones-global-net-zero-framework-for-shipping-for-one-year/>, 2025.
- [5] International Maritime Organisation (IMO), Fourth IMO Greenhouse Gas Study, 2020.
- [6] European Commission, Regulation (EU) 2023/1805 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 on the use of renewable and low-carbon fuels in maritime transport, and amending Directive 2009/16/EC (Text with EEA relevance). https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-modes/maritime/decarbonising-maritime-transport-fueles-maritime_en, 2023 (accessed July 5, 2025).

- [7] R. (CE D. Laursen, R.; Sofiadi, D.; Nelissen, D.; Király, J.; van der Veen, Synthetic Fuels for Shipping, 2024.
- [8] A. Tremel, P. Wasserscheid, M. Baldauf, T. Hammer, Techno-economic analysis for the synthesis of liquid and gaseous fuels based on hydrogen production via electrolysis, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 40 (2015) 11457–11464, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.01.097>.
- [9] Methanol Institute, Marine Methanol: Future-Proof Shipping Fuel, 2023.
- [10] International Maritime Organisation (IMO), Methanol as Marine Fuel: Environmental Benefits, Technology Readiness, and Economic Feasibility, 2016.
- [11] American Bureau of Shipping, Methanol Bunkering: Technical and Operational Advisory, 2024.
- [12] J. Harmsen, N. Nesterova, C. Bekdemir, K. Van Kranenburg, Green Maritime Methanol WP2 Initiation and Benchmark Analysis. www.tno.nl, 2020.
- [13] Methanol Institute, Methanol Safe Handling Manual, 5th edition, 2020.
- [14] Methanol Institute, Atmospheric above Ground Tank Storage of Methanol. <http://www.methanol.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/atmosphericabovegroundstorage.pdf>, 2016.
- [15] P. Battaglia, G. Buffo, D. Ferrero, M. Santarelli, A. Lanzini, Methanol synthesis through CO₂ capture and hydrogenation: thermal integration, energy performance and techno-economic assessment, *J. CO₂ Util.* (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2020.101407>.
- [16] H. Gelten, Y. Hajimolana, W. de Jong, B. Heesink, H. Nami, B. Aalderink, R. van Leeuwen, Power-to-methanol: techno-economic analysis of a regional, decentral case study, *Fuel* 405 (2026) 136528, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2025.136528>.
- [17] K. Atsonios, K.D. Panopoulos, E. Kakaras, Investigation of technical and economic aspects for methanol production through CO₂ hydrogenation, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 41 (2015) 2202–2214, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.12.074>.
- [18] Y. Rahmat, S. Maier, F. Moser, M. Raab, C. Hoffmann, J.U. Repke, R.U. Dietrich, Techno-economic and exergy analysis of e-methanol production under fixed operating conditions in Germany, *Appl. Energy* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.121738>.
- [19] S. Sollai, A. Porcu, V. Tola, F. Ferrara, A. Pettinau, Renewable methanol production from green hydrogen and captured CO₂: a techno-economic assessment, *J. CO₂ Util.* 68 (2023) 102345, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2022.102345>.
- [20] N. Meunier, R. Chauvy, S. Mouhoubi, D. Thomas, G. De Weireld, Alternative production of methanol from industrial CO₂, *Renew. Energy* (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2019.07.010>.
- [21] C. Siskos, P. Manakas, L. Karagoanoglou, A. Vlysidis, Techno-economic and environmental analysis of methanol production from cement carbon dioxide emissions, *Renew. Energy* (2026), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.124109>.
- [22] M. Yousaf, A. Mahmood, A. Elkamel, M. Rizwan, M. Zaman, Techno-economic analysis of integrated hydrogen and methanol production process by CO₂ hydrogenation, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2022.103615>.
- [23] M. Bampaou, K. Panopoulos, P. Seferlis, A. Sasiain, S. Haag, P. Wolf-Zoellner, M. Lehner, L. Rog, P. Rompalski, S. Kolb, N. Kieberger, S. Dettori, I. Matino, V. Colla, Economic Evaluation of Renewable Hydrogen Integration into Steelworks for the production of Methanol and methane, *Energies* (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15134650>.
- [24] I. Matino, S. Dettori, A.S. Conde, V. Colla, A. Petruccianni, A. Zaccara, V. Iannino, C. Mucci, A. Hauser, S. Kolb, J. Karl, P. Wolf-Zoellner, S. Haag, M. Bampaou, K. Panopoulos, E. Heracleous, N. Kieberger, K. Rechberger, L. Róg, P. Rompalski, Hydrogen intensified synthesis processes to valorise process off-gases in integrated steelworks, *Mater. Tech.* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1051/mattech/2023025>.
- [25] W. Uribe-Soto, J.F. Portha, J.M. Commenge, L. Falk, A review of thermochemical processes and technologies to use steelworks off-gases, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 74 (2017) 809–823, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.03.008>.
- [26] European Commission, Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/1185 of 10 February 2023 Supplementing Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council by Establishing a Minimum Threshold for Greenhouse Gas Emissions Savings of Recycled Carbon Fuels and B, 2023.
- [27] Hydrogen France, Position Paper on the Use of Industrial CO₂ to Produce e-Fuels - Delegated Act from Article 28 (5) of RED2, 2023.
- [28] A. Tozlu, Techno-economic assessment of a synthetic fuel production facility by hydrogenation of CO₂ captured from biogas, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 47 (2020) 3306–3315, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.12.066>.
- [29] G. Lombardelli, S. Consonni, A. Conversano, M. Mureddu, A. Pettinau, M. Gatti, Process design and techno-economic assessment of biogenic CO₂ hydrogenation-to-Methanol with innovative catalyst, *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2385/1/012038>.
- [30] M. Matzen, M. Alhajji, Y. Demirel, Chemical storage of wind energy by renewable methanol production: Feasibility analysis using a multi-criteria decision matrix, *Energy* (2015), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2015.09.043>.
- [31] M. Bampaou, V. Mitrousis, E. Koliyamitra, P. Stratigousis, H. Schloesser, I. Matino, V. Colla, K.D. Panopoulos, Bio-CO₂ as feedstock for renewable methanol in maritime applications, *Energies* (2026) 1–41.
- [32] T. Zitscher, M. Kaltschmitt, Sustainable carbon utilization for a climate-neutral economy—framework necessities and assessment criteria, *Energies* 17 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17164118>.
- [33] E. Koliyamitra, V. Mitrousis, T. Kraia, G. Kardaras, N. Lazaridou, T. Grekou, K. Fotiadis, D. Koutsonikolas, A. Asimakopoulou, M. Bampaou, K.D. Panopoulos, Capture, sampling and analysis of biogenic CO₂ streams for methanol synthesis, *Membranes* (Basel). (2026), <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes16030106>.
- [34] L.M. Recolons, Optimal Scenarios for Wind-to-Methanol: Techno-Economic Analysis, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 2024.
- [35] D.S. Marlin, E. Sarron, Ó. Sigurbjörnsson, Process Advantages of Direct CO₂ to Methanol Synthesis, *Front. Chem.* (2018), <https://doi.org/10.3389/fchem.2018.00446>.
- [36] M. Bampaou, S. Haag, A.-S. Kyriakides, K.D. Panopoulos, P. Seferlis, Optimizing methanol synthesis combining steelworks off-gases and renewable hydrogen, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.113035>.
- [37] U. Khan, C.C. Ogbaga, O.A.O. Abiodun, A.A. Adeleke, P.P. Ikubanni, P.U. Okoye, J.A. Okolie, Assessing absorption-based CO₂ capture: Research progress and techno-economic assessment overview, *Carbon Capture Sci. Technol.* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccs.2023.100125>.
- [38] E. Meuleman, A. Cottrell, A. Ghayur, Treatment of flue-gas impurities for liquid absorbent-based post-combustion CO₂ capture processes, Elsevier Ltd, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100514-9.00022-6>.
- [39] P. Arango Munoz, Stripper Modification of a Standard MEA Process for Heat Integration with a Pulp Mill. <http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:skth:diva-289162>, 2020.
- [40] Chemical Safety Data Sheet MSDS / SDS Monoethanolamine. <https://www.chemicalbook.com/msds/ethanolamine.htm>, 2025 (accessed February 5, 2026).
- [41] M. Ellison, S. Barzagar, L. Nguyen, R. Harvey, C. Dimopoulos, R. Robinson, Review of emissions from post-combustion carbon capture using amine based technologies and current monitoring techniques, 2022.
- [42] M. Salimi, V. Karimi, F. Hosseini, F. Amidpour, Techno-economic study of different process configurations of CO₂ capture by MEA absorption and utilization of an MCDM method for their ranking, *Energy Rep.* (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyr.2024.06.043>.
- [43] S.M. Soltani, P.S. Fennell, N. Mac Dowell, A parametric study of CO₂ capture from gas-fired power plants using monoethanolamine (MEA), *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control*. (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2017.06.001>.
- [44] S.Y.W. Chai, L.H. Ngu, B.S. How, Review of carbon capture absorbers for CO₂ utilization, *Greenh. Gases Sci. Technol.* (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1002/ghg.2151>.
- [45] AspenTech, ENRTL-RK Rate-based Model of the CO₂ Capture Process by MEA using Aspen Plus - Version 10.0. <http://www.aspentech.com>, 2008.
- [46] M. Amirkhosrow, J.F. Pérez-Calvo, M. Gazzani, M. Mazzotti, E. Nemat Lay, Rigorous rate-based model for CO₂ capture via monoethanolamine-based solutions: effect of kinetic models, mass transfer, and holdup correlations on prediction accuracy, *Sep. Sci. Technol.* (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1080/01496395.2020.1784943>.
- [47] M. Garcia, H.K. Knuutila, S. Gu, ASPEN PLUS simulation model for CO₂ removal with MEA: Validation of desorption model with experimental data, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2017.08.024>.
- [48] B.H. Li, N. Zhang, R. Smith, Rate-based modelling of CO₂ capture process by reactive absorption with MEA, *Chem. Eng. Trans.* (2014), <https://doi.org/10.3303/CET1439003>.
- [49] S. Sebbahi, A. Assila, A. Alaoui Belghiti, S. Laasri, S. Kaya, E.K. Hlil, S. Rachidi, A. Hajjaji, A comprehensive review of recent advances in alkaline water electrolysis for hydrogen production, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.07.428>.
- [50] B.N.D. van Haersma Buma, M. Peretto, Z.M. Matar, G. van de Kaa, Towards renewable hydrogen-based electrolysis: Alkaline vs Proton Exchange Membrane, *Heliyon* 9 (2023) e17999, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e17999>.
- [51] T. Wang, X. Cao, L. Jiao, PEM water electrolysis for hydrogen production: Fundamentals, advances, and prospects, *Carbon Neutrality* (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43979-022-00022-8>.
- [52] European Hydrogen Observatory, The European hydrogen market landscape, 2025.
- [53] A. Badgett, J. Brauch, A. Thatte, R. Rubin, C. Skangos, X. Wang, R. Ahluwalia, B. Pivovar, M. Ruth, Updated Manufactured Cost Analysis for Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers, *Natl. Renew. Energy Lab.*, 2023. <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy24osti/87625.pdf>.
- [54] J. Park, K. Hwan Ryu, C.H. Kim, W. Chul Cho, M.J. Kim, J. Hun Lee, H.S. Cho, J. H. Lee, Green hydrogen to tackle the power curtailment: meteorological data-based capacity factor and techno-economic analysis, *Appl. Energy* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.121016>.
- [55] A. Solyanik, Analysis of cost efficiency of hydrogen production via electrolysis: the Russian case study, *E3S Web Conf.* 289 (2021) 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202128904002>.
- [56] M. Bampaou, K.D. Panopoulos, An overview of hydrogen valleys: current status, challenges and their role in increased renewable energy penetration, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2024.114923>.
- [57] S.G. Simoes, J. Catarino, A. Picado, T.F. Lopes, S. di Bernardino, F. Amorim, F. Gírio, C.M. Rangel, T. Ponce de Leão, Water availability and water usage solutions for electrolysis in hydrogen production, *J. Clean. Prod.* (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128124>.
- [58] A. Franco, C. Giovannini, Recent and future advances in water electrolysis for green hydrogen generation: Critical analysis and perspectives, *Sustainability* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152416917>.
- [59] F. Eckl, A. Moita, R. Castro, R.C. Neto, Valorization of the by-product oxygen from green hydrogen production: a review, *Appl. Energy* (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.124817>.

- [60] R. Cvetkovska, L. Wechner, T. Kienberger, Techno-economic assessment of hydrogen supply solutions for industrial site, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.09.099>.
- [61] M. Bampaou, K.D. Panopoulos, P. Seferlis, S. Voutetakis, Evaluation of novel hydrogen integration options in bio-oils introduction to petrochemical refineries, *Energy* 254 (2022) 124353, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.124353>.
- [62] F. Manenti, S. Cieri, M. Restelli, G. Bozzano, Dynamic modeling of the methanol synthesis fixed-bed reactor, *Comput. Chem. Eng.* (2013), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2012.09.013>.
- [63] I. Matino, S. Dettori, A. Zaccara, A. Petrucciani, V. Iannino, V. Colla, M. Bampaou, K. Panopoulos, K. Rechberger, S. Kolb, A. Hauser, P. Wolf-Zöllner, S. Haag, N. Kieberger, P. Rompalski, Hydrogen role in the valorization of integrated steelworks process off-gases through methane and methanol syntheses, *Mater. Tech.* (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1051/mattech/2022009>.
- [64] O. Tursunov, L. Kustov, A. Kustov, A brief review of carbon dioxide hydrogenation to methanol over copper and iron based catalysts, *Oil Gas Sci. Technol.* (2017), <https://doi.org/10.2516/ogst/2017027>.
- [65] C. Pirola, G. Bozzano, F. Manenti, Fossil or Renewable Sources for Methanol Production? Elsevier B.V., 2018 <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63903-5.00003-0>.
- [66] G. Bozzano, F. Manenti, Efficient methanol synthesis: Perspectives, technologies and optimization strategies, *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.peccs.2016.06.001>.
- [67] B. Lacerda de Oliveira Campos, K. John, P. Beeskow, K. Herrera Delgado, S. Pitter, N. Dahmen, J. Sauer, A detailed process and techno-economic analysis of Methanol synthesis from H₂ and CO₂ with intermediate condensation steps, *Processes* (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr10081535>.
- [68] M. Bertau, H. Offermanns, L. Plass, F. Schmidt, H.J. Wernicke, Methanol: The basic Chemical and Energy Feedstock of the Future: Asinger's Vision Today, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-39709-7>.
- [69] ISO 6583:2024, Methanol as a Fuel for Marine Applications — General Requirements and Specifications, 2024.
- [70] M. Bampaou, A.-S. Kyriakides, K. Panopoulos, P. Seferlis, S. Voutetakis, Modelling of methanol synthesis: improving hydrogen utilisation, *Chem. Eng. Trans.* 88 (2021) 931–936, <https://doi.org/10.3303/CET2188155>.
- [71] S.H.T. Oelmann, M. Gorny, T. Schuhmann, M. Strozyk, F. Castillo-Welter, C. Drosdzol, A new reactor concept for conversion of CO₂ to methanol, *Oil Gas Eur. Mag.* (2021), <https://doi.org/10.19225/211208>.
- [72] E. Vesterinen, Methanol Production Via CO₂ Hydrogenation, Aalto University School of Engineering, 2018.
- [73] M. Bampaou, K. Panopoulos, P. Seferlis, S. Voutetakis, I. Matino, A. Petrucciani, A. Zaccara, V. Colla, S. Dettori, T. Annunziata Branca, V. Iannino, Integration of renewable hydrogen production in steelworks off-gases for the synthesis of methanol and methane, *Energies* (2021), <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14102904>.
- [74] K.D.T. Max S. Peters, *Plant Design and Economics for Chemical Engineers*, Fifth, McGraw-Hill, 2003.
- [75] S.Y. Ereev, M.K. Patel, Standardized cost estimation for new technologies (SCENT) - methodology and tool, *J. Bus. Chem.* 9 (2012) 31–48.
- [76] D.R. Woods, *Rules of Thumb in Engineering Practice*, Wiley, 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527611119>.
- [77] I. Dejanovi, L. Matija, Designing a packed dividing wall column for an aromatics processing plant, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* (2011), <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie1020206>.
- [78] X. Xu, B. Xu, J. Dong, X. Liu, Near-term analysis of a roll-out strategy to introduce fuel cell vehicles and hydrogen stations in Shenzhen China, *Appl. Energy* 196 (2017) 229–237, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.11.048>.
- [79] A.Z. Charlotte van Leeuwen, *Innovative Large-Scale Energy Storage Technologies and Power-to-Gas Concepts after Optimisation*, 2020.
- [80] A. Mayyas, M. Ruth, B. Pivovar, G. Bender, K. Wipke, A. Mayyas, M. Ruth, B. Pivovar, G. Bender, K. Wipke, Manufacturing cost Analysis for Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers, *Natl. Renew. Energy Lab.*, 2019, p. 65. <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy10osti/72740.pdf>. <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy10osti/72740.pdf>. <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy10osti/72740.pdf>.
- [81] European Commission, Hydrogen Generation in Europe: Overview of Costs and Key Benefits. <https://www.apren.pt/contents/publicationsothers/hydrogen-generation-in-europe.pdf>, 2020.
- [82] K. Spoof-Tuomi, T.A. Manfo, Techno-Economic Analysis of Green Hydrogen Production- 20 MW PEM Electrolysis Plant, 2025.
- [83] W. Sparber, W. Weiss, B. Sanner, L. Angelino, M. De Gregorio, N. Février, W. Haslinger, A. Kujbus, S. Landolina, G. Striy-Hipp, W. Helden, Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda 2021–2027 of Clean Hydrogen Joint Undertaking, 2022.
- [84] European Central Bank, (2026). https://www.ecb.europa.eu/stats/policy_and_exchange_rates/euro_reference_exchange_rates/html/eurofxref-graph-usd.en.html (accessed January 28, 2026).
- [85] Eurostat, Hourly Labour Costs. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Hourly_labour_costs, 2026 (accessed January 28, 2026).
- [86] J. Sillman, A. Ylä-Kujala, J. Hyppiä, T. Kärrri, M. Tuomaala, R. Soukka, Feasibility assessment of e-methanol value chains: temporal and regional renewable energy, costs, and climate impacts, *Appl. Energy* 391 (2025) 125887, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2025.125887>.
- [87] Eurostat, Electricity Prices for Non-household Consumers - Bi-Annual Data (from 2007 Onwards). https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nrg_pc_205_custom_18723473/default/table, 2026 (accessed January 28, 2026).
- [88] Business Analytiq, Monoethanolamine Price Index, in: <https://businessanalytiq.com/procurementanalytics/index/monoethanolamine-price-index/>, 2026 (accessed January 28, 2026).
- [89] O.M. Hubert, D. Peterson, E. Miller, J. Vickers, R.M. Doe, Clean Hydrogen Production Cost Scenarios with PEM Electrolyzer Technology, 2024.
- [90] Ship & Bunker, Rotterdam Bunker Prices. https://shipandbunker.com/prices/emea/nwe/nl-rtm-rotterdam#_MEOH, 2026 (accessed January 28, 2026).
- [91] International Energy Agency (IEA), Global Hydrogen Review 2023, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1787/cb2635f6-en>.
- [92] H.B. and R.M. (IRENA) and M.C. (Forschungszentrum J. Emanuele Taibi, T. study was supervised by D.G. and R.R. (IRENA), Green Hydrogen Cost Reduction: Scaling up Electrolysers to Meet the 1.5°C Climate Goal, 2020.
- [93] IRENA (International Renewable Energy Agency), Biomass for Heat and Power, 2015.
- [94] X. Sun, J. Alcalde, M. Bakhtbidar, J. Elfo, V. Vilarrasa, J. Canal, J. Ballesteros, N. Heinemann, S. Haszeldine, A. Cavanagh, D. Vega-Maza, F. Rubiera, R. Martínez-Orio, G. Johnson, R. Carbonell, I. Marzan, A. Travé, E. Gomez-Rivas, Hubs and clusters approach to unlock the development of carbon capture and storage – Case study in Spain, *Appl. Energy* (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117418>.
- [95] M. Ebrahimzadeh Sarvestani, O. Norouzi, F. Di Maria, A. Dutta, From catalyst development to reactor design: a comprehensive review of methanol synthesis techniques, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 302 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2024.118070>.
- [96] T. Svitnič, K. Sundmacher, Cost-scaling of large Power-to-Methanol plants supplied with wind power and CO₂ from direct air capture: a Chile case study, *Energy. Convers. Manage.* 345 (2025) 120343, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2025.120343>.
- [97] C.M. Douglas, H. Lai, M. Ostadi, W. Shin, L. Bromberg, G. Zang, Techno-economic analysis and life-cycle assessment of methanol synthesis plants using renewable hydrogen and carbon dioxide feedstocks, *Energy. Convers. Manage.* 347 (2026) 120374, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2025.120374>.
- [98] M. Pavlík, F. Kurimský, K. Ševc, Renewable Energy and Price Stability: an Analysis of volatility and Market Shifts in the European Electricity Sector (2015–2025), *Appl. Sci.* 15 (2025) 6397, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app15126397>.
- [99] IRENA (International Renewable Energy Agency), Renewable Generation Costs In 2024, 2024.
- [100] Ghassan Wakim, Hydrogen Production Via Electrolysis the Limits of Potential Cost Declines, 2023.
- [101] Ø. Ulleberg, S. Sartori, Simulating offshore hydrogen production via PEM electrolysis using real power production data from a 2.3 MW floating offshore wind turbine, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.03.471>.
- [102] International Energy Agency, Is Carbon Capture Too Expensive?. <https://www.iea.org/commentaries/is-carbon-capture-too-expensive>, 2026 (accessed January 28, 2026).
- [103] M. Bampaou, K.D. Panopoulos, A comprehensive overview of technologies applied in hydrogen valleys, *Energies* (2024), <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17246464>.
- [104] Nordic Energy Research, Nordic Criteria for Hydrogen Valleys and Hydrogen Hotspots, (2026). <https://pub.norden.org/nordicenergyresearch2024-04/2-nordic-criteria-for-hydrogen-valleys-and-hydrogen-hotspots.html> (accessed January 28, 2026).
- [105] Clean Hydrogen Partnership, Hydrogen Valley Platform. <https://h2v.eu/>, 2026 (accessed January 28, 2026).
- [106] Global CCS Institute, *Understanding Industrial CCS Hubs and Clusters*, 2016.
- [107] S.G. Subraveti, K. Hansen, R. Anantharaman, C. Fu, S. Gardarsdottir, D. Kim, J. A. Ouassou, S. Roussanly, CO₂ capture from multiple sources: to be, or not to be clustered, that is the question, *Carbon Capture Sci. Technol.* (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cst.2025.100422>.
- [108] SmartPort, Power-2-Fuel Cost Analysis. https://smartport.nl/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Cost-Analysis-Power-2-Fuel_def_2020.pdf, 2020.
- [109] G. Zomer, S. Finner, J. Harmsen, L. Vredeveltd, P. van Lieshout, Green Maritime Methanol Operation Aspects and the Fuel Supply Chain. <https://publications.tno.nl/publication/34637282/W1qAIG/TNO-2020-R11105.pdf>, 2020.
- [110] TNO, A supply chain cost analysis-Green maritime methanol. www.tno.nl, 2023.
- [111] A. Elwalily, E. Verkama, F. Mantei, A. Kaliyeva, A. Pounder, J. Sauer, F. Nestler, Sustainable aviation fuel production via the methanol pathway: a technical review, *Sustain. Energy Fuels* 9 (2025) 5151–5180, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d5se00231a>.
- [112] Methanol Institute, Economic Value of Methanol for Shipping under Fuel EU Maritime and EU ETS. https://methanol.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/ECONOMIC-VALUE-OF-METHANOL-FOR-SHIPPING-PAPER_final.pdf, 2024.
- [113] International Maritime Organisation, The IMO Net-Zero Framework - FAQs, (2026). <https://www.imo.org/en/mediacentre/hottopics/pages/faqs-the-imo-net-zero-framework.aspx> (accessed April 5, 2026).
- [114] Global CCS Institute, Carbon Contracts for Difference in Europe, 2025.
- [115] Z. He, M. Liu, J. Siu, L. Lam, I. Halimi, Evaluating the techno-economic feasibility and social impact of methanol as a marine fuel, *J. Clean. Prod.* 533 (2025) 146999, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.146999>.
- [116] IFP Energies nouvelles, Life cycle assessment of e-/bio- methanol and e-/grey-/blue- ammonia for maritime transport, 2025.
- [117] A. Ingwersen, A.J. Hahn, S. Pfister, J.N. Peel, R. Sacchi, C. Moretti, Prospective life cycle assessment of cost-effective pathways for achieving the FuelEU

- Maritime Regulation targets, *Sci. Total Environ.* 958 (2025) 177880, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.177880>.
- [118] J.L. Bravo, J.A. Rocha, J.R. Fair, Mass transfer in gauze packing, *Hydrocarb. Process* 64 (1985) 91–95.
- [119] T.H. Chilton, A.P. Colburn, Mass transfer (Absorption) coefficients prediction from data on heat transfer and fluid friction, *Ind. Eng. Chem.* (1934), <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie50299a012>.
- [120] J.J.A.R.J.F. Bravo, A comprehensive model for the performance of column containing structured packing, *ICHEME Symp. S* (1992) 128A439–128A453.